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Iberian Digital Media
Observatory

IBERIFIER — Iberian Digital Media Observatory

Spain & Portugal fact-checking brief

Q4 – September 2025 - November 2025

This quarterly report collects the main hoaxes and disinformation narratives detected in Spain and Portugal from September to November 2025 by the fact-checking organisations integrated into the IBERIFIER hub.

Find more information at: www.iberifier.eu

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1. Most repeated hoaxes and disinformation campaigns

September 2025 – November 2025

In Spain

- Disinformation narratives focused on migration in Europe, including alleged crimes committed by migrants and supposed threats to Christmas markets by Muslim immigrants.
- In Spanish politics, misinformation revolved around alleged corruption cases, the trial of the Attorney General, the implementation of V-16 emergency beacons, claims of preferential treatment toward Moroccan products such as poultry and olive oil, and the 50th anniversary of Franco's death.
- The war in the Gaza Strip generated misleading content, particularly during peace negotiations, as well as narratives linked to protests in Spain against Israeli attacks and to Nobel Peace Prize nominations.
- Disinformation related to the United States also increased significantly. The main themes concerned the alleged assassination of Charlie Kirk and the election of Zohran Mamdani as mayor of New York.
- Additional narratives involved avian influenza outbreaks and the use of paracetamol during pregnancy.

In Portugal

- Disinformation narratives around immigration continue to circulate, particularly targeting Muslim immigrants. False claims have emerged about alleged attacks on Catholic churches by Muslim migrants.
- In Portuguese politics, proposed amendments to the Foreigners Law and the approval of a bill banning face-covering garments, such as burqas or niqabs, in public spaces have also been exploited. Misleading content has linked immigrants to overburdened public infrastructure and alleged undue fiscal benefits.
- During the Local Elections and at the start of the presidential election debates, disinformation narratives intensified, particularly after the derailment of the Elevador da Glória in September 2026. Immigration-related narratives gained prominence, including false statements attributed to candidates and the amplification of decontextualized positions.
- At the international level, disinformation was particularly notable around the trial and conviction of former Brazilian president Jair Bolsonaro. In the United States, narratives proliferated around the alleged assassination of Charlie Kirk and the election of Zohran Mamdani as mayor of New York.
- The conflict in the Gaza Strip also fueled disinformation, including narratives involving Portuguese deputy Mariana Mortágua's participation in the Humanitarian Flotilla.

- Online scams grew significantly, particularly via text messages, phishing, and false offers.
- Additional narratives concerned COP30, the use of paracetamol during pregnancy, and topics related to artificial intelligence.

1. Cases of cross mis- and disinformation (Spain-Portugal)

Across both Spain and Portugal, several disinformation narratives were recurrent. Migration was a central theme, with false claims linking Muslim immigrants to crimes, attacks on churches, and threats to public spaces or cultural events such as Christmas markets. Political narratives in both countries exploited allegations of government favouritism toward immigrants at the expense of the local population.

At the international level, disinformation related to the United States appeared in both contexts, focusing on the assassination of Charlie Kirk and the election of Zohran Mamdani. The conflict in the Gaza Strip also generated misleading content, particularly regarding the Humanitarian Flotilla and protests in both countries.

The narratives common to both countries included several topics, but the main one linked taking paracetamol during pregnancy to an increased risk of autism, with [Maldita](#), [Newtral](#), [EFE Verifica](#) and [Polígrafo](#) reporting on it.

2. Main hoaxes

In Spain

- An increase in disinformation narratives targeting immigrants, particularly Muslims, has been observed. Within this broad topic, multiple false claims have been identified across several subthemes. At the European level, with the approach of the holiday season, [allegations circulated regarding an alleged mass cancellation of Christmas markets due to supposed threats from Muslim immigrants](#) and [protests against Christmas celebrations](#). [Other false claims suggested that Muslims tend to avoid migrating to Muslim-majority countries](#), instead overwhelmingly choosing countries with a Christian tradition. There were also [unfounded assertions about the implementation of practices such as Sharia law](#) in various European countries.
- In the Spanish context, these narratives were linked to an [alleged rise in sexual assaults, purportedly associated with the presence of people from countries stereotyped as misogynistic](#), as well as baseless claims [regarding improper payments to unaccompanied young migrants](#), implying that [only foreigners benefited from social support measures](#). Additionally, there were misleading claims about adaptations made by the government to avoid offending Muslim students, [such as the prohibition of pork consumption](#). See more [here](#) and [here](#).

- In November, controversy around V-16 beacons intensified; these beacons are mandatory for all vehicles in Spain from January 1, 2026. [The main narratives claimed](#) that they were a tool [to control the population](#), that [they were dangerous](#), or that their mandatory adoption was the result of a corrupt scheme.
- [Disinformation also emerged regarding alleged corruption cases in Spain, including the trial and conviction of the Attorney General of the State for revealing secrets, which generated political controversy.](#) See more [here](#) and [here](#). These were accompanied by claims of supposed [government favoritism toward Moroccan products](#), such as [poultry and olive oil](#).
- Within national politics, there was also the [circulation of disinformation around the 50th anniversary of the death of Francisco Franco](#). See more [here](#) and [here](#).
- In Spain, several disinformation narratives also circulated about events in the United States. Key topics included the assassination of Charlie Kirk, with significant [manipulation of his statements](#) and [the motivations for the crime](#) on social media; and [the election of Zohran Mamdani as mayor of New York](#), including allegations about [communist tendencies](#) and [religious influence \(Muslim\)](#).
- At the international level, [narratives focused on the conflict in the Gaza Strip, especially during peace negotiations, the movement of the Humanitarian Flotilla to Gaza, and protests in Spain](#) against Israeli attacks. Other narratives referred to the [Nobel Peace Prize nominations, killings of Christians in Africa](#) and [viral misattributed footage from Gaza](#).
- In the field of health, disinformation circulated [denying the existence of avian influenza, pointing to an alleged conspiracy linked to Morocco](#), as well as messages, [based on statements by Donald Trump](#), discouraging the [use of paracetamol during pregnancy](#). See more [here](#).

In Portugal

- Disinformation narratives targeting immigration, particularly Muslim migrants, continue to increase. False claims have circulated about alleged attacks on Christian churches by Muslim immigrants, most recently in [Wales](#) and [Canada](#).
- In Portugal, proposed amendments to the Foreigners Law have been linked to [content portraying immigrants as overburdening public infrastructure](#) and being falsely [favored in access to childcare](#). The approval of a bill banning face-covering garments, such as burqas or niqabs, in public spaces has also been exploited. Key narratives targeted a [Muslim journalist who wears a hijab, falsely claiming she is not a real Muslim](#). Immigration was also used during the Local Elections through the [circulation of fake posters depicting alleged left-wing candidates as Sikh](#). The same

occurred at the start of the presidential election debates, with [false claims attributed to candidates promoting increased immigration to the country](#).

- The derailment of the Elevador da Glória in Lisbon was exploited to [spread disinformation during the Local Elections campaigns](#), as well as to attack the government, [falsely claiming it had not declared mourning for the summer fire victims](#).
- The Humanitarian Flotilla to the Gaza Strip was a highly fertile topic for disinformation, particularly due to the participation of left-wing politician Mariana Mortágua. Key false claims included alleged [stops during the trip for parties in Ibiza](#), AI-altered images, [videos of her detention by Israeli forces](#), and the [circulation of a petition supposedly signed by thousands demanding she never be released](#). Additionally, disinformation falsely claimed that [the left wing organized demonstrations in support of Hamas on October 7](#).
- [The trial and conviction of the former president of Brazil gave rise to multiple false claims](#), including [exaggerated reports of massive protests](#) and attempts to link [Jair Bolsonaro to Donald Trump](#).
- Disinformation regarding the United States had two main focuses: the assassination of Charlie Kirk, with narratives [falsely attributing statements to him](#) and [circulating supposed videos of his killer fleeing](#) and [being arrested](#), and [his alleged support for Donald Trump](#); and the election of Zohran Mamdani, accompanied by [narratives claiming possible fraud in his election](#) and the [alleged implementation of Sharia law in New York](#).
- There was a significant increase in online scams. Notable examples included [messages requesting payments on behalf of banks and companies](#) and fraudulent claims [from public](#) and [government figures offering large sums of money](#).
- [Statements by Donald Trump about the alleged dangers of taking paracetamol during pregnancy triggered alarmist narratives](#). Additional disinformation narratives concerned [COP30](#).

3. Main disinformation narratives

In Spain

- With the approach of the holiday season, social media saw a proliferation of false claims regarding the famous markets set up in various European cities, particularly

in Germany. AI-generated images and other out-of-context photos were circulated, purportedly showing scenes from these markets. Many of these disinformation pieces were accompanied by messages against the Muslim community. These claims are linked to the Great Replacement theory and the criminalization of migrants, which has been increasingly observed.

- Claims have circulated suggesting that the Spanish government is allocating funds to African countries instead of addressing local needs. In November, several pieces of content specifically referenced Spanish funds directed to African nations.
- Narratives have circulated suggesting that the EU allows imports that harm Spain's primary sector and that foreign food imports threaten local food sovereignty. Several examples of these claims emerged following an outbreak of avian influenza in Spain.
- There was a significant increase in disinformation regarding the implementation of V-16 beacons in Spain, mandatory from January 1, 2026. These false narratives suggested that the beacons were a state surveillance and control measure, represented an unnecessary expense, or even hid a “new tax,” fueling public outrage. The most prominent narrative claimed that authorities or an elite wanted to constantly monitor citizens as part of a plan to establish a silent dictatorship.
- Narratives have circulated claiming that vaccines are responsible for multiple adverse effects and health risks. These claims resurfaced with the start of the seasonal influenza vaccination campaign.
- Disinformation around the assassination of Charlie Kirk aligns with U.S. political conflicts, aiming to attack Kirk’s figure (a prominent Republican) and link the killer to the rival party. Conspiracy theories without evidence also implicated Israel in the assassination. Some narratives tried to associate the trans community with any firearm attack occurring in the country. These narratives are linked to U.S. partisan politics and broader conspiracies about minority groups.
- The election of Zohran Mamdani as mayor of New York sparked narratives focusing on an alleged “Muslim invasion” of the West, linking to Great Replacement-type narratives. Other narratives spread claims of electoral fraud, fitting into broader anti-Western or anti-democratic narratives.
- Following the trial and conviction of the Attorney General, disinformation claimed that the government would either take revenge on the judges who convicted him or reward him with a new position, tying into anti-government and anti-European narratives questioning institutional impartiality.
- One disinformation narrative claimed that there was no famine crisis occurring in the Gaza Strip, using out-of-context images from markets where food was visible and asserting that Palestinians were not being attacked by Israel but were instead using actors. Major disinformation narratives about the Humanitarian Flotilla accused it of not delivering aid or claimed its crew was partying and indifferent to Gaza’s situation, aiming to discredit the initiative.

In Portugal

- Disinformation narratives targeting immigration, particularly Muslim communities, continued to circulate. In Portugal, amendments to the Foreigners Law were framed through content portraying immigrants as overburdening public services and being unfairly favoured in access to childcare. During local and presidential election periods, fake posters and fabricated statements attributed to candidates promoted narratives of increased immigration. The content reinforced Great Replacement-type fears and sought to heighten perceptions of cultural threat and institutional bias.
- The Humanitarian Flotilla to the Gaza Strip generated multiple false claims, particularly due to the participation of Mariana Mortágua. Allegations included supposed party stops in Ibiza, AI-manipulated images, and fabricated videos of her detention. These claims functioned to discredit the initiative and cast doubt on the credibility of left-wing political actors regarding Middle East issues.
- The trial and conviction of the former president of Brazil led to exaggerated reports of mass protests and attempts to link Jair Bolsonaro to Donald Trump. Such narratives attempted to frame the events within broader transnational political alignments, amplify polarisation, and create a perception of widespread popular support for Bolsonaro.
- In the United States, disinformation focused on the assassination of Charlie Kirk, including fabricated statements and misleading videos seeking to legitimise the attack. The election of Zohran Mamdani was accompanied by claims of electoral fraud and the alleged implementation of Sharia law in New York. This content was designed to intensify partisan divisions and introduce Great Replacement-type narratives to the U.S. context.
- There was also an increase in online scams, including fraudulent payment requests impersonating banks, companies, and public figures. These schemes exploited public trust for financial gain.
- Statements by Donald Trump regarding the alleged risks of paracetamol during pregnancy triggered alarmist narratives, while additional false claims targeted COP30. In these cases, the disinformation sought to generate fear and undermine confidence in public health and environmental initiatives.

In Latam

- Reforms by Javier Milei affect employment, taxes, and the justice system (Argentina).
- False statements by political figures regarding the assassination of Carlos Manzo (Mexico).
- False claims about proposals and actions of Gustavo Petro and his circle (Colombia).

- Military tension between the United States and Venezuela in the Caribbean (Venezuela).

4. Main hoaxes according to topics

Environment - Climate

- [The circulation of AI-generated images of Hurricane Melisa was used to spread misinformation and attack climate agencies.](#) (Newtral)
- [Narratives attacking climate agencies and denying climate change were amplified online.](#) (Newtral)
- [Bill Gates was falsely presented as admitting climate change is a lie.](#) (Newtral)
- [Claims that EU low-emission zones harm citizens were spread as disinformation.](#) (Newtral)
- [Misrepresentation of EU fishing restrictions created misleading narratives.](#) (Newtral)
- [The 2030 Agenda promotes sustainable forest management; it does not prohibit clearing forests in Spain.](#) (AFP España)
- [The mining operation in Oencia, Spain, was approved before the August 2025 wildfire.](#) (AFP España)
- [Solar panels are falsely accused of destroying traditional crops, being highly polluting, and releasing toxic substances.](#) See more [here](#). (Maldita.es)
- [Meat and dairy products were falsely blamed as major causes of climate change to justify bans.](#) (Maldita.es)
- [Claims that climate policies are driven by fanaticism and exaggeration are debunked by scientific consensus.](#) (Verificat)
- [The circulation of manipulated or misleading footage of Hurricane Melissa was used to amplify climate-related disinformation.](#) See more [here](#). (Polígrafo)
- [False claims about dramatic incidents during COP30, including a ship on fire, were shared to discredit the climate summit.](#) (Polígrafo)
- [Misleading narratives alleged that Greta Thunberg travelled to Brazil for COP30 under controversial circumstances.](#) (Polígrafo)

Gender

- [Disinformation circulated about gender exams in sports and critiques of feminism and women's situation in Islamic or other religions, as well as issues related to the LGBTBIQ+ community.](#) (Newtral)
- [Claims about women being taken hostage by Hamas spread online.](#) (Newtral)
- [False reports about child weddings in Gaza were circulated.](#) (Newtral)
- [French female boxers were falsely accused of being men due to gender tests.](#) (Newtral)
- [The false claim that Brigitte Macron was born a man continues to circulate.](#) (Maldita.es)
- [Claims that a significant number of gender violence reports are false are misleading; actual investigations show only 0.02% may involve false complaints.](#) (Verificat)
- [A digitally manipulated image of Greta Thunberg was circulated to sexualise and discredit her public image.](#) (Polígrafo)

Migration & racism

- [Narratives alleged that immigrants receive the Minimum Vital Income or benefit from the so-called "Ley Esperanza." See more \[here\]\(#\).](#) (Newtral)
- [Replacement narratives and misleading claims about students in Denmark were circulated online.](#) (Newtral)
- [Viral stories falsely portrayed violent incidents involving a Scottish girl with an axe and children sleeping on the floor in US immigration detention centres.](#) See more [here](#). (Newtral)
- [El vídeo donde un "policía musulmán" de servicio reza en un andén de metro fue generado por IA.](#) (AFP España)
- [The women wearing niqabs in a viral video were not filmed in London, but in Indonesia.](#) (AFP España)
- [Europe and the Spanish government are falsely accused of facilitating Moroccan imports to harm Spanish farmers and livestock producers.](#) See more [here](#) and [here](#). (Maldita.es)
- [Authorities are falsely accused of banning pork to avoid offending Muslims.](#) See more [here](#). (Maldita.es)

- [Claims that Sharia law is being adopted in European countries have been widely debunked](#). See more [here](#). (Maldita.es)
- [Narratives alleging that radical Muslims are burning Christian churches in Western countries circulate without evidence](#). See more [here](#). (Maldita.es)
- [Narratives claim that foreigners do not work and live off welfare benefits instead of contributing to the economy](#). (Verificat)
- [Claims that the Catalan government is replacing Catalan culture with Arab/Muslim culture through Arabic classes in schools are misleading](#). (Verificat)
- [The claim that 85 % of the world's refugees are Muslim was circulated to suggest an overwhelming association between migration and Islam](#). (EFE Verifica)
- [The claim that abortion support and family aid programs were designed to benefit large Muslim families as part of a supposed "Kaleergi Plan" circulated online to suggest deliberate demographic engineering](#). (EFE Verifica)
- [Videos and images falsely claimed that churches in Wales and Canada were burned down by Muslim immigrants, reinforcing anti-migrant narratives](#). See more [here](#). (Polígrafo)
- [Narratives suggested that immigrant children are given priority over Portuguese citizens in public nurseries](#). (Polígrafo)
- [Claims circulated that more than 500,000 immigrants had recently entered the Portuguese health system, framing migration as a burden](#). (Polígrafo)
- [The allegation that a journalist presented as Muslim was in fact "fake" or secretly not Muslim was shared online to question her identity and discredit her reporting](#). (Polígrafo)

Celebrities

- Several disinformation narratives targeted Donald Trump, including a [manipulated video allegedly showing him with Bill Clinton](#), a [miscaptioned photo of Ivanka and Donald Trump](#), [false claims that he planned to ban iPhone and Samsung to promote a Tesla smartphone linked to Elon Musk](#), and allegations that [he announced the confiscation of migrants' property](#). (Newtral)
- [Narratives falsely claimed María Corina Machado was exiled](#). (Newtral)

- [The Spanish politician Isabel Díaz Ayuso changed her bio on X regarding Israel in 2019, not in 2025.](#) (AFP España)
- [The image of former Spanish minister Irene Montero with her “Filipina maid” was created using AI.](#) (AFP España)
- [Supposed donations involving famous tennis players like Carlos Alcaraz were invented to gain visibility on Facebook.](#) (Maldita.es)
- [The claim that Cristiano Ronaldo was offering €2,500 to users who entered a special promotional code on a website circulated online as part of a fraudulent giveaway scheme.](#) (Polígrafo)

Politics

- [The 50th anniversary of the death of dictator Francisco Franco on November 20th prompted the spread of disinformation about his figure and false or decontextualized content glorifying his legacy.](#) See more [here](#) and [here](#). (Newtral)
- [Supposed police operations were claimed to reveal corruption by Spanish politicians.](#) See more [here](#). (Maldita.es)
- [The claim that national mourning was declared for a train derailment but not for deadly wildfires was shared online to suggest double standards in official responses to national tragedies.](#) (Polígrafo)
- [The claim that President Marcelo was traveling to Germany to attend a “hamburger festival” funded by taxpayers emerged from a mistranslation of “Bürgerfest,” an event celebrating civic engagement.](#) (Polígrafo)
- [The claim that María Corina Machado asked the United States to bomb Venezuela and that Donald Trump was disqualified from the Nobel Peace Prize circulated online.](#) (EFE Verifica)

Elections

New York, United States of America

- [False claims were spread about Zohran Mamdani’s political victory.](#) (Newtral)
- [False narratives portrayed New York mayor-elect Zohran Mamdani as a communist or radical Islamist intending to abolish private property or impose](#)

[Islamic practices](#). See more [here](#). (Maldita.es)

Local Elections, Portugal

- [A misleading video alleged electoral fraud involving migrant voters in Portugal](#). (Polígrafo)
- [The claim that an image shows three Indo-Pakistani and Muslim candidates from PS, Livre and BE in the local elections was circulated to frame Portuguese political parties as being overtaken by foreign or religious interests](#). (Polígrafo)
- [The claim that Carlos Moedas was the first mayor to regulate tourism in Lisbon was shared to credit him uniquely for policies that had already been implemented by previous administrations](#). (Polígrafo)

Health

- [Conspiracy-type disinformation narratives falsely deny the existence of avian flu or suggest a connection with Morocco](#). See more [here](#) and [here](#). (Newtral)
- [Avian flu was falsely portrayed as a fraud that does not affect birds](#). (Maldita.es)
- [False claims spread by US President Donald Trump discouraged the use of paracetamol during pregnancy without scientific evidence](#). See more [here](#). (Newtral)
- [Sunglasses do protect against eye damage, contrary to what a Spanish footballer claimed](#). (AFP España)
- [Claims that paracetamol use during pregnancy is linked to autism were circulated online](#). (Maldita.es)
- [The circulation of false claims linking COVID-19 vaccination to cancer diagnoses was used to create fear and mistrust around vaccines](#). See more [here](#) and [here](#). (Maldita.es)
- [The so-called post-abortion syndrome is not a medically recognized condition, despite a Madrid City Council initiative promoting it](#). (Verificat)
- [The claim that flu vaccines for children cause narcolepsy was circulated to create fear and distrust around childhood immunization](#). (EFE Verifica)

- [Claims falsely linked paracetamol use during pregnancy to an increase in autism cases.](#) (Polígrafo)

Security

- [SMS messages alleging suspicious debits in bank accounts were shared online to induce panic and solicit sensitive information from recipients.](#) (Polígrafo)
- [The claim that squatting has spiralled out of control in Spain and that the government is lax or complicit in tolerating it was circulated to fuel public anxiety and distrust in authorities.](#) (Newtral)
- [The claim that squatting has spiralled out of control in Spain, that the government is lax or complicit, and that the issue is being obscured or manipulated by artificial intelligence or media, was circulated to fuel public anxiety and distrust in authorities.](#) See more [here](#). (Newtral)
- [The allegation that the V-16 vehicle beacon can geolocate citizens even when turned off was circulated to promote fears of pervasive state surveillance and loss of personal privacy.](#) (Maldita.es)
- [The claim that higher rates of sexual violence in Spain are caused by the presence of people from “misogynistic cultures” was circulated to scapegoat foreign populations, despite evidence that gender-based violence is a broader social issue.](#) (Verificat)
- [The claim that a person was detained for reporting on social media about the rape of a woman by immigrants circulated online; in fact, the detention was part of an anti-drug operation.](#) (EFE Verifica)

Sexuality

- [Misleading narratives targeted Marc Márquez in relation to LGBT+ pride in MotoGP.](#) (Newtral)
- [Homonationalist narratives claim that Vox defends Spanish homosexuals while proposing cuts to the rights and freedoms of the LGBTQ+ community.](#) (Verificat)
- [False statements alleged that a Palestinian TV presenter called for the killing of all homosexuals.](#) (Polígrafo)

Others | Israeli–Palestinian Conflict

- [Disinformation circulated about the Gaza ceasefire and the flotilla heading to Gaza.](#) See more [here](#). (Newtral)
- [Manipulated or misleading content circulated about Portuguese political figures involved in humanitarian flotillas towards Gaza.](#) See more [here](#). (Polígrafo)
- [False claims circulated about public demonstrations in Portugal connected to the October 7 anniversary.](#) (Polígrafo)

5. Verifications on content created with Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence-driven fact-checks were carried out by all fact-checkers.

In both Portugal and Spain, AI-generated and digitally manipulated disinformation is primarily widespread across international conflicts, politics, immigration, and climate events.

The Middle East conflict, particularly the Israel-Hamas situation and the Humanitarian Flotilla, has been a major focus of AI-based misinformation. Notable examples include [AI-generated images portraying flotilla members in holiday-like settings](#) or [provocative attire](#), as well as [fabricated images of the flotilla's landing in the Gaza Strip](#), allegedly [showing them encountering weapons](#).

The topic of immigration has also been targeted by AI, often focusing on the supposed “Muslim invasion.” False images have circulated showing [large groups of women wearing hijabs in parts of Spain](#), [police in France pausing their work to perform Muslim prayers](#), and [schools in England allegedly teaching children to pray](#). AI-generated content has also depicted anti-immigration demonstrations in the UK, [exaggerating the size of the crowds](#).

Climate and natural disasters are another major focus. Hurricane Melissa, for example, [prompted manipulated videos](#) and [AI-generated images](#) exaggerating impacts in [Jamaica](#) and [Cuba](#), as well as [false depictions of floods in Catalonia](#).

In this context, Maldita.es has published several guides aimed at [alerting and explaining the periods of AI-related disinformation](#), covering topics such as [cyberattacks](#) and [health](#).

6. Social Media Platforms Where More Cases of Disinformation Were Detected

X was the most mentioned platform (all 6 fact-checkers contributing to this report identified it as the main platform for information dissemination). WhatsApp, Instagram and Tiktok were each mentioned once, while Facebook was mentioned twice.

Average number of verifications by fact-checkers in the quarter: 311

7. Disinformation trends that have been detected in Latin America

In the fourth quarter of 2025, these were the main disinformation trends identified in Latin America:

- **Migration:** The United States' migration policy solidified throughout 2025 as one of the main topics of disinformation. In the last quarter, posts were identified containing false government measures either [benefiting](#) or [harming](#) the migrant population, as well as [AI-generated videos showing expulsions by the Immigration and Customs Enforcement \(ICE\)](#).
- **Elections:** During the presidential elections in Bolivia, [Chile](#), and Honduras in the last quarter, alongside the legislative [elections in Argentina](#), false content circulated that is common in the region, such as [fake statements by candidates](#) and [allegations of electoral fraud](#) based on common voting errors. There was a significant increase in [AI-generated disinformation](#) compared to elections in previous years.
- **Scams:** At the regional level, scams continued to be frequent content across social media, using repeated strategies to capture users' attention. In the last quarter, ads [promising supposed government benefits](#) and promoting investments featuring [AI-generated videos of public figures](#) predominated.
- **Venezuela–United States conflict:** The threat of a U.S. intervention in Venezuela during the final months of 2025 led to the spread of [false posts](#) showing [supposed arrivals of American troops](#) before such an intervention took place in early 2026.
- **COP30:** During the United Nations event in Brazil, disinformation targeting the government of Lula Da Silva was identified, as well as [AI-generated videos of protests by indigenous groups](#). Additionally, while the event was taking place, [videos questioning the urgency of climate change without scientific evidence](#) began circulating on social media, some of which had already been published previously.

This section of the report results from a collaboration between several Latin American fact-checkers and IBERIFIER. The participating organizations are: [Animal Político](#) (Mexico), [Cazadores de Fake News](#) (Venezuela), [La Silla Vacía](#) (Colombia), and [Chequeado](#) (Argentina). This initiative is part of the Observatory's broader objective to expand its scope beyond the Iberian Peninsula and tackle the challenge of disinformation within the Portuguese and Spanish speaking regions.

To identify the main disinformation trends at the regional level, we used as our source the Q4 2025 report published by LatamChequea (the network of Latin American fact-checking organizations).

The report is based on information gathered from 26 LatamChequea partner organizations across 16 countries and is part of the project "Promoting reliable information and fighting disinformation in Latin America", coordinated by Chequeado.

The full report is available [here](#).

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Fact-checkers that have contributed to this report

SPAIN

[AFP España](#)

[EFE Verifica](#)

[Maldita.es](#)

[Newtral](#)

[Verificat](#)

PORTUGAL

[Polígrafo](#)

IBERIFIER – Iberian Digital Media Observatory

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal funded by the European Commission, linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). It is made up of thirteen universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and five multidisciplinary research centers.

Its main mission is to analyze the Iberian digital media ecosystem and tackle the problem of misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

1. Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.
2. Development of computational technologies for the early detection of misinformation.
3. Fact-checking of misinformation in the Iberian territory.
4. Strategic reports on threats of disinformation, both for public knowledge and for the authorities of Spain and Portugal.
5. Promotion of media literacy initiatives, aimed at journalists and informants, young people and society as a whole.

For more information look for the project website iberifier.eu and the Twitter account [@iberifier](https://twitter.com/iberifier).

Website: iberifier.eu

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Associate

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